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ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF MUTUAL PROTECTION OF CHILDREN'S RIGHTS AND CULTURAL HERITAGE DURING MILITARY CONFLICTS

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Summary. *In the article, in the period of military conflicts, the issues of mutual relation between the protection of children's rights and that of cultural heritage are widely analyzed with the existing diversity of opinions in the legal literature and important international documents. First of all, mutual analysis of defense issues in two important directions on the problem is justified. Then, the main provisions of the important international norms adopted in both directions are addressed. At the same time, the internal normative-legal acts adopted by the Republic of Azerbaijan in these directions are analyzed and the necessity of their improvement is justified. Thus, it is noted that currently in the Republic of Azerbaijan, activities are being carried out in the direction of adopting the Children's Code as a more efficient form in the field of ensuring children's rights, which should be taken as a positive step.*

The article also reviews international organizational mechanisms in this direction. In particular, the activities of the Committee on the Rights of Child and UNESCO in this field are noted. At the same time, the role of regional mechanisms is justified by specific cases.

In the end, a number of important conclusions are reached by analyzing the interrelationship issues of two important directions, such as the protection of children's rights and cultural heritage during military conflicts: both directions are directly based on the human rights factor; enough international agreements have been adopted in both directions; there is a need to further improve international control mechanisms in both directions; it should be noted the necessity of mutual functioning and improvement of internal defense means in both directions; it is necessary to implement appropriate domestic measures (legislative, administrative, etc.) to ensure the effectiveness of international legal norms in both directions; it is necessary to adopt new international agreements in both directions, which should clearly include international control systems; it is necessary to take a number of important steps within the framework of UNESCO as an important international organization that will organize protection and coordination at the international level in both directions, etc.

Keywords. *military conflicts, children's rights, human rights, cultural heritage, international agreements, international organizations, international humanitarian law, cultural rights, principles of children's rights.*

The protection of human rights during military conflicts attracts attention with a number of important directions and relevance. Although the mechanisms of human rights protection and its guarantee allow achieving more serious results in peacetime, it is impossible to achieve this efficiency during military conflicts. Therefore, from both a theoretical and a practical point of view in research, a more

serious approach to the protection of human rights during military conflicts is required [10; 11]. This requires taking a number of important steps to solve the problem from the context of both international and domestic law. Thus, it is necessary to analyze the protection issues in two important directions for the mentioned problem:

- protection of children's rights as a whole during military conflicts;
- protection of cultural heritage during military conflicts.

In general, the protection of human rights during military conflicts includes a fairly wide system of relations and norms. In addition to being called "international humanitarian law" as an important field of international law, this direction also consists of two important sections: "Hague law" and "Geneva law" [5, p. 36-40]. The "Hague Law" which includes the Hague international documents of 1899 and 1907 is mainly aimed at limiting the methods and means of waging war, while the "Geneva Law" formed on the basis of the Geneva Conventions of 1949 is mainly aimed at the legal protection of war victims. Thus, the "Hague Law", which was initially created, was later radically changed. Its principles and norms were focused on the protection of war victims, and its scope expanded significantly. In its modern form, "Geneva law" or "genuine humanitarian law" is derived from the four Geneva Conventions of 1949 (Geneva Convention for the Amelioration of the Condition of the Wounded and Sick in Armed Forces in the Field; Geneva Convention for the Amelioration of the Condition of Wounded, Sick and Shipwrecked Members of Armed Forces at Sea; Geneva Convention relative to the Treatment of Prisoners of War; Geneva Convention relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War) and two Additional Protocols to them dated 1977 (Protocol I for the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflicts and Protocol II for the Protection of Victims of Non-International Armed Conflicts).

Numerous other international conventions and agreements also act as sources of international humanitarian law. For example, the 1948 Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide, the 1954 Hague Convention on the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict, the 1972 Convention on the Prohibition of the Development, Production and Stockpiling of Bacteriological (Biological) and Toxin Weapons and on their Destruction, the 1976 Convention on the Prohibition of Military or any other Hostile Use of Environmental Modification Techniques, the 1980 Convention on Prohibitions or Restrictions on the Use of Certain Conventional Weapons Which May Be Deemed to Be Excessively Injurious or to Have Indiscriminate Effects and Additional Protocols, etc.

When talking about children's rights as a component of human rights, it is rightly noted in the legal literature that the specificity of children's rights requires a

deeper and slightly different approach to the problem. Children's mental and physical development characteristics, lack of life experience, and to a certain extent dependent on parents, not always being able to apply to the relevant authorities for the protection of their rights and legal interests, finally defining a number of different rights accordingly (living in a family, the right to care by parents, etc.) should be specially mentioned in this sense. In addition, as more facts about the deprivations and abuses suffered by children are revealed, the efforts of the international community to strengthen children's rights are increasing [3, p. 140-141].

In general, with the important international documents adopted in the direction of the protection of children's rights, in particular with the International Convention on the Rights of the Child dated 1989, a number of specific principles have been distinguished in this field, which covers the period of military conflicts as a whole, including relations related to the protection of cultural heritage. These principles include: no discrimination against children; ensuring the best interests of children; expressing each child's own thoughts independently and freely; ensuring children's right to healthy development; providing special protection to children; special approach to children in each area; the principle of international cooperation in the field of ensuring children's rights [1, p. 41-44]. In addition, although the adoption of the 1924 Declaration of the Rights of the Child, including the 1959 Declaration of the Rights of the Child, could not impose important obligations on the states in this area, the International Convention on the Rights of the Child dated 1989 established important international obligations on the states in this area, at the same time, confirmed important features in a number of directions: to confirm the human rights defined within the framework of other international agreements in relation to children as a whole; to strengthen a number of fundamental rights of children, taking into account their specific characteristics; to set international standards in areas relevant to children, etc.

The Geneva Declaration on the Rights of the Child, adopted by the League of Nations in 1924 and consisting of 5 principles, attracted attention with a number of important provisions in the field of child rights protection. For example, children should be the first to receive help in a disaster; the child must be freed from all forms of exploitation [4, p. 331]. In the Declaration of 1959, adopted later, for the first time, it was unequivocally stated that children have certain rights (for example, the right to name and citizenship, the right to education, etc.).

Article 2, part 1 of the 1989 International Convention on the Rights of the Child states that the States Parties, regardless of the race, color, sex, language, religion, political or other beliefs, national-ethnic or social origin, property status, health and circumstances of birth or any other circumstances of the child, his or her parents or legal guardians, respect and guarantee all the rights set forth in

this Convention for every child within their jurisdiction without discrimination. Then, in Article 4 of that Convention, it is stated that the states parties take the necessary legislative, administrative and other measures for the implementation of the rights recognized in this Convention. They take such measures on economic, social, and cultural rights within the maximum framework of their resources and, if necessary, within the framework of international cooperation.

In general, during military conflicts, two important aspects such as the protection of children's rights and cultural heritage are characterized by their seriousness and interrelated with each other. Children belong to a special group of the population related to sensitivity and require a special approach to the processes by the state. According to Article 5 of the 1974 Declaration on the Protection of Women and Children in Emergency and Armed Conflict, States party to the military conflict must make all possible efforts to protect women and children from the destructive effects of war, and should achieve the cancellation of persecution, torture, degrading treatment and violence, etc. Legal literature rightly notes that there are concrete scientific explanations for why children suffer more from military conflicts than other civilian populations. First of all, children suffer more damage from the consequences of military conflicts because they are at a sensitive stage of their vital development, that is, children who are victims of military conflicts retain the traces of that military conflict for a long time in their future development compared to adults. Second, compared to adults, children are less able to adapt to conflict situations and take adequate steps to deal with them. Thirdly, children who are victims of military conflicts face serious financial (poverty, destitution, tendency to crime), social (drug addiction, various diseases), and moral (deprivation of parental care, mental disorders, dropping out of education) violations after those conflicts. Fourth, during the protection of children's rights, the state, society, and family feel the need to constantly pay special attention to them [7, p. 4].

People enjoy rights under any circumstances and at any time, including times of military conflict, and the observance of those rights is an international obligation of states. All persons not directly participating in military operations have the right to respect their personality and honor, exercise their family and religious rights, and demand humane treatment in various circumstances. Article 77 of Additional Protocol I of 1977 to the Geneva Conventions of 1949 states that children enjoy special respect and protection against any form of indecent assault. Parties to the conflict undertake to provide protection and assistance to children, regardless of age or otherwise.

Article 4 of the 1977 Additional Protocol II to the 1949 Geneva Conventions on the Protection of Victims of Non-International Armed Conflicts entitled

"Fundamental Guarantees" states that children are provided with the necessary care and assistance during non-international military conflicts. In addition, Article 38 of the 1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child obliges States parties to take all possible measures to ensure the protection of children involved in military conflict.

Article 17 of the Fourth Geneva Convention of 1949 on the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War directly states that children must be evacuated from besieged or occupied areas. On the other hand, Article 49 of the same Convention states that if the occupying state carries out a partial evacuation from any region, that state must ensure that members of the same family are not separated from each other. In addition, Additional Protocol II of 1977 to the Geneva Conventions of 1949 provides for the accompaniment of children in the absence of parents or guardians by persons responsible for their safety and well-being.

The Fourth Geneva Convention of 1949 on the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War gives special importance to the situation of children separated from their parents and orphans. In this case, the statistics in the world are not good at all. In addition, based on Article 50 of the Fourth Geneva Convention, the occupying parties are prohibited from changing the family or personal status of children. Thus, during an international military conflict, changing the nationality or citizen status of children is inadmissible. Then, in accordance with Article 51 of the same international document, the occupying parties are prohibited from involving persons under the age of 18 in forced labor.

The most serious moral blow inflicted on children during military conflicts is the deprivation of their right to education. When educational institutions are destroyed and opportunities for education are destroyed, children are forced to leave their homes and away from schools, and such children in conflict situations become illiterate and grow up without the necessary knowledge. According to the Third Geneva Convention of 1949 relative to the Treatment of Prisoners of War, the party that has prisoners of war and forcibly detained persons under its control during military conflicts must carry out intellectual, educational, and sports activities in relation to those persons. According to Article 38 of that Convention, the party to the conflict must take all the necessary measures for the performance of the activities mentioned in relation to this category of persons and provide them with the relevant places. Education must be provided to children and adolescents, whether they attend schools in or outside detention facilities. These provisions also apply to orphans and children separated from their parents as a result of military conflict. When realizing children's right to education, the parties must follow spiritual, moral, religious, and cultural values.

In addition, according to the Fourth Geneva Convention of 1949 and Additional Protocol I for the Legal Protection of War Victims, children should have freer access

to cultural heritage during international military conflicts. Then, in Article 24 of that international document, it is stated that the parties to the conflict ensure that all necessary measures related to religion and education are taken for children under 15 years of age, orphans, or children who are separated from their families. If possible, the upbringing of children from this category should be entrusted to people with the same cultural values, customs, and traditions. In addition, Article 68 of the same Convention prohibits the death penalty for persons under the age of 18. At the same time, Article 76 states that a special regime should be applied to minors detained in the occupied territory, those persons should be kept separately from other prisoners if possible.

Returning children who are victims of military conflict to their communities is the most effective means of their reintegration. Here, special importance should be given to the acquisition of education and means of living. The most effective way to help out-of-school children and adolescents is to enable them to enroll in or return to school. However, unfortunately, children in conflict zones are deprived of the opportunity to go to school and eat. 50 percent of all children of primary school age who do not have access to education live in countries where hostilities are taking place. Currently, approximately 57 million children do not attend educational institutions (8). The main reason for this sad situation is military conflicts.

Other important international documents have also been adopted in this field. For example, the 1990 World Declaration on the Survival, Protection and Development of Children; 2000 Optional Protocol on the Involvement of Children in Armed Conflict to the 1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child; 2006 Integrated Disarmament, Demobilization and Reintegration Standards; 2007 Paris Guiding Principles and Commitments on Children Associated with Armed Groups and Armed Forces; 2011 Optional Protocol on a Communications Procedure to the 1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child, and etc.

The 2000 Optional Protocol to the 1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child raised the minimum age for direct participation in military operations and military service to 18 years. The Committee on the Rights of the Child, established in accordance with the International Convention on the Rights of the Child dated 1989, has also determined the number of principles in this field by considering the reports submitted by the states on the implementation of the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Involvement of Children in Armed Conflict (for example, children should not be involved in military operations; punishment of the use of children in military conflicts; restoration and reintegration of the rights of children who are victims of military conflicts, especially cultural rights; international assistance and cooperation, etc.). The 1990 African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of Children, adopted within the framework of the African

region, established the African Committee of Experts on monitoring the realization of those rights by establishing broad rights and freedoms for children.

As already mentioned, children also belong to the category of "everyone" and all the rights generally attributed to human rights belong to them. In a general sense, the classification of human rights is mainly carried out in three groups: civil and political rights, known as first-generation rights; second-generation rights, which include economic, social, and cultural rights; the third or new generation of human rights emerging in modern times.

Cultural rights, which have a special place in the system of human rights, ensure the moral development of a person and help each individual to become a worthy follower of political, moral, social, and cultural progress. These rights are special complex human rights and freedoms provided by legislation, which enable a person to realize himself in the cultural and scientific field. The main provisions in this regard are detailed in the 1966 International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights. Cultural rights also protect the public way of life, which is important to many members of society, as the use of culture or participation in cultural life is essential to a decent way of life (6, p. 218-219). In Article 40 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the right to culture reflects the following elements: everyone has the right to participate in cultural life, and to use cultural institutions and cultural resources; everyone should respect historical, cultural, and spiritual heritage, take care of it, protect historical and cultural monuments (12).

Every child has the right to participate in the process of exercising their cultural rights in their group. No one can be excluded or deprived from this group. All states have an important responsibility in this area for children. The deprivations for children who are forced to lose their homes during military conflicts are extreme. When children are forced to leave their places of residence, they are forced to settle in other areas after passing difficult and dangerous roads for days. In addition, there is a gross violation of the right to recreation, which is contained in Article 31 of the 1989 Convention on the Rights of the Child. The lack of conditions also leads to the violation of their right to leisure time. This is a violation of children's right to play. Thus, these children, displaced from their native places, are left out of their cultural groups and societies, and increasingly forget the values of the cultural community.

One of the special principles of international humanitarian law, the *ratione logi* (principle of the object) or the principle of limitation by objects, combines the following important provisions on the problem mentioned in it: it is forbidden to attack undefended places; it is prohibited to allow any hostile actions directed against buildings where scientific research is conducted or charitable institutions

are located, and historical monuments, works of art, or places of religious worship that constitute the cultural and spiritual heritage of nations; it is forbidden to attack facilities and buildings if dangerous forces can be created from them for the civilian population; the civilian population cannot be used to protect military objects from attacks; civilian objects cannot be the object of attack or pressure measures; it is forbidden to destroy or relocate objects necessary for the life of the civilian population; robbery is prohibited.

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights dated 1948 states that the provision of cultural rights determines the future of society. Cultural rights protect the rights of each person to expand their worldview, to develop their own values, beliefs, convictions, and folklore with their own way of life. These rights are also based on the cultural heritage and resources that support development processes. This resulted in the adoption of sufficient international documents in the mentioned direction. First of all, universal international documents (1954 Convention on the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict, 1972 Convention on the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, 2005 Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions, 2003 Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage, 1970 Convention on the Means of Prohibiting and Preventing the Illicit Import, Export and Transfer of Ownership of Cultural Property, etc.), then regional international documents (1989 European Convention for the Protection of Architectural Heritage, 1954 European Cultural Convention, 1985 European Convention on Offences relating Cultural Property, 1992 European Convention on the Protection of Archaeological Heritage, 2005 European Framework Convention on the Value of Cultural Heritage for Society, 1976 San Salvador Convention on the Protection of the Archaeological, Historical and Artistic Heritage of the American Nations, etc.), in addition to normative norms or "soft" legal norms (the UNESCO Recommendation of 1956 on the International Principles Applicable to Archaeological Excavations, the UNESCO Recommendation of 1976 concerning the Safeguarding and Contemporary Role of Historic Areas, UNESCO Recommendation of 1976 concerning the International Exchange of Cultural Property, UNESCO Recommendation of 1989 on the Safeguarding of Traditional Culture and Folklore, Recommendation of 1994 on the Protection of the Cultural Heritage of the Parliamentary Assembly of the Black Sea Economic Cooperation Member Countries, Recommendation of 2004 on the improvement and protection of the cultural heritage of the member states of the Black Sea Economic Cooperation Organization, etc.), and finally bilateral international agreements (2010 Agreement on Strategic Partnership and Mutual Assistance between the Republic of Azerbaijan and the Republic of Turkey, etc.) should be noted.

International experience shows that the importance of protecting cultural resources is especially relevant during military conflicts. First of all, the 1954 Convention on the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict plays an important role in the regulation of those relations (2, p. 113-114). At this time, UNESCO, a specialized institution of the UN, acts as an international organizational mechanism in the mentioned field. It is necessary to adopt sufficient international documents in the field of cultural heritage protection within the framework of UNESCO, as well as to take a number of steps that will organize protection and coordination at the international level in two important areas, such as the protection of children's rights and cultural heritage during military conflicts, despite the existence of international control mechanisms within the organization.

The Republic of Azerbaijan, which participates in important international agreements in the field of human rights, including children's rights, adopted the Law on Children's Rights dated May 19, 1998, which regulates the comprehensive protection of children's rights. The important rights of children are reflected in the law in the following order: equal rights of children (Article 6); the child's right to life and development (Article 8); the right to protect the child's life and health (Article 9); the child's right to a name and citizenship (Article 10); the child's right to education (Article 11); the child's right to liberty and security (Article 12); the child's right to necessary maintenance (Article 13); the child's freedom of conscience, opinion and speech (Article 14); the child's freedom of information (Article 15); the right of the child to live in the family (Article 17); the right of a child living apart from his parents (Article 18); rights and duties of parents (Article 19); the child's right to housing (Article 20); the child's right to inheritance and custody at the expense of his parents' property (Article 21); children's right to rest (Article 25); the right of children to join public organizations (Article 26); the right to protection of the child's honor and dignity (Article 27); and so on. According to Article 37 of the Law, important provisions related to ensuring the protection of children in accordance with international legal norms in areas involved in military conflicts, transferring children in the zone of hostilities to safe places, using all possible opportunities for the protection of their life and health, direct prohibition of the participation of children under the age of 15 in military operations and involvement of children in military educational institutions are reflected (9).

Currently, in the Republic of Azerbaijan, activities are being carried out towards the adoption of the Children's Code as a more effective form of ensuring children's rights, which, in our opinion, should be taken as a positive step.

Thus, a number of important conclusions can be reached by analyzing the interrelationship issues of two important areas such as the protection of

children's rights and cultural heritage during military conflicts:

- both directions are directly based on the human rights factor as the main basis;
- enough international agreements have been adopted in both directions;
- there is a need to further improve international control mechanisms in both directions;
- it should be noted the necessity of mutual functioning and improvement of internal defense means in both directions;
- it is necessary to implement relevant domestic measures (legislative, administrative, etc.) to ensure the effectiveness of international legal norms in both directions;
- it is necessary to adopt new international agreements in both directions, which should clearly include international control systems;
- it is necessary to take a number of important steps within the framework of UNESCO as an important international organization that will organize protection in both directions and coordination at the international level, etc.

References:

1. ADILOV, N.A. Protection of children's rights in modern international law and legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan: theoretical and practical issues. Baku, 2010, 287 p.
2. ALIYEV, A.I. Azerbaijan in the target of international crimes: legal analysis (in Azerbaijani, French, English, Russian and Turkish). Baku, 2018, 176 p.
3. ALIYEV, A.I. Human rights. Textbook. Baku, 2019, 352 p.
4. CONSTANCE, L. Shehan. The Wiley Blackwell Encyclopedia of Family Studies, 4 Volume Set, Volume 1, John Wiley & Sons, 2016, 2280 p.
5. DAVID, E. Principles of the law of armed conflicts. Course of lecture. Moscow, International Committee of the Red Cross, 2011, 1144 p.
6. DONNELLY, J. Universal Human Rights in theory and Practice. Second edition. Cornell University Press. Ithaca-London, 2003, 290 p.
7. GASIMOVA, A.M. Protection of the rights of the child during military conflicts in modern international law. Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy. Specialty: 5603.01 – „International law; human rights”. Baku, 2021, 30 p.
8. Information initiative „TheWorldOnly”. Link: <http://theworldonly.org/uroven-obrazovaniya-mire/>
9. Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on children's rights. Link: www.e-qanun.az
10. MAMMADOV, R.F., AFANDIYEVA, H.E. International legal protection of historical and cultural monuments of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Baku, 2015, 328 p.
11. SULEYMANLI, S.A. Problems of international legal regulation of cultural heritage protection and legislation of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Baku, 2018, 296 p.
12. The Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Link: www.e-qanun.az

